

TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS FOR STUDENT SERVICE UNIT STAFF MEMBERS BASED ON NEEDS ANALYSIS

¹Dilfuza Ulugbaeva, ¹Malika Kamilova, ²Dildara Gapparova, ²Nargiza Alinazarova

^{1,2,4}Graduate, Master of Human Resource Management and Talent Development, Westminster International University in Tashkent

³Course Leader, MA in Human Resource Management and Talent Development, Westminster International University in Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10829552>

Abstract. Talent Development programs help organization to upgrade skills of employee as a result employee show performance via working within an organization. Therefore, this research explored Training and Development Programs for Student Service Unit at an international university in Tashkent. The participants of survey were key members of Student Service Unit and data collection was obtained via providing semi-structured interviews.

Keywords: Talent Development, Training Programs, Student Service Unit, Need Analysis.

1.0 Introduction

It is important for organizations to develop the capabilities and knowledge of current employees because it will help them not lose stability in different circumstances, and they should focus on the development of employees who will play important roles when the entities meet futures challenges (CIPD, 2009). The training development programmes for administration staff at the university is crucial for improving quality and efficiency of service which they provide to students. There are several reasons why there may be a need for Talent Development programs for Students Service Units:

(a) Increasing Competitions; (b) Changing student demographics; (c) Technological advancement; (d) Enhancing student satisfaction; (e) Professional growth and motivation. Training Need Analysis may provide information about employees' efficiency level, the skill areas most in need and the ways which this might be achieved (Ludwikowska, 2018). Denby (2010) stated that, Training Needs Analysis is an essential activity in designing training programs, analysis of organization's efficiency level and defining systematic investigation.

2.0 Literature Review

Training Needs Assessment is the organizational process of gathering and analysing data that enhances decision making for selecting trainings which may be best option to develop individuals' performances, clarifying who should be trained, and making what content should be taught (Clarke, 2003). Training Needs Analysis represents differences between employees' current performance and performance that entities expect of them (Mager and Pipe, 1979). Wright and Geroy (1992) claim that TNA should collect, analyse, and interpret data on individual, group and organizational skill gaps and it has seven key characteristics: (a) considering culture and organizational philosophy; (b) being proactive; (c) having method that allows differences between situations that can be addressed via training and those that cannot; (d) Allowing interested and involved ones to participate; (e) considering observable skills; (f) using data analysis and sampling techniques; (g) having cost/benefit analysis.

3.0 Methods

This study utilizes qualitative methods, focusing on semi-structured interviews with key members of the Student Services Unit (SSU) at an international university in Tashkent. Interviews

aim to uncover perspectives on talent development needs, organizational goals, and individual career aspirations. Thematic analysis of interview data will identify common training needs. Based on these findings, tailored training programs aligned with organizational goals will be designed and implemented.

4.0 Results

4.1 *Manager of Student Services Unit*

The first chosen employee for the interview is the manager of Student Services Unit (SSU). According to the SSU manager, one of the main tasks of her is to fully ensure the administrative responsibilities to provide effective services to students while complying with all management and compliance requirements. The Manager of SSU stressed that the primary aim of the organization is to get customer satisfaction, specifically students. In her point of view, gaining the satisfaction of the students does not only depend on the academic staff of the institute, but also it should involve the administrative staff.

Based on his 8 years of work experience, she noted that students always want to participate in the social life of the institute and spend their free time effectively. Students often come to the Student Services Unit (SSU) desk to learn about upcoming events and to ask how they can contribute. Even in their summer holiday, students come to the institute to participate the admission process and help new comers. Sometimes, it is difficult to involve all the students to such processes and most of them get upset. In her (manager of SSU) opinion, to handle the problem and to effectively manage student participation Volunteer Association of the university should be developed. Currently, the university has the volunteers' association, but it is not officially opened as a department. During orientation week when new students join the institute, facilitators are attached to each group and they tell to their student that the institute have the volunteer association. Student who are willing to take part in the social life of the institute can join by coming to SSU. According to her, as a manager, she is facing the challenge of running this volunteer association. She also said that there is not clear procedures (documentation) on how to manage the association.

Besides, when it is asked "What is your expectations from the company after 5 years? In what position do you see yourself?" she replied (smiling) 'I do not know, maybe Senior Manager of Admission and Student Administration'. She considers herself to have all the necessary skills, which senior managers should have, and enough experience to be promoted after five years.

4.2 *Assistant Manager of Student Services Unit*

The second interview was made with the assistant manager of the Student Services Unit. She had more than three years of experience working as an assistant manager. She noted that her performance appraisal results are the best ones among her colleagues, meaning that currently she acquires the necessary skills and abilities to work in the position. Moreover, twice a year the survey is conducted to evaluate the coordinators (every assistant manager works as a coordinator for particular level of students) and she always gets satisfactory results from her students anonymously. She clearly stated that her aim within one year is to reach the position that is senior assistant manager of Student Services Unit, consequently manager of SSU after 4 or 5 years.

However, she also highlighted that to be able to work efficiently as a senior assistant manager of SSU she needs additional skills and competences. For example, she believes that to accomplish all the tasks of the senior assistant manager successfully, one should know how to inspire the team, should have the capability to persuade and direct subordinates or other groups in an organization. Moreover, she emphasized that she is very kind person in her personality and she thought that

kindness might be a barrier when challenging task have to be divided among the team fairly. Because, in most cases, she prefers to handle all the tasks by herself instead of planning and organizing, according to the assistant manager of SSU.

5.0 Discussion and Recommendation

5.1. Training for the manager of Student Services Unit

According to the response of SSU manager, they need well-established Volunteers Association (VA) that involves all the procedures on how to organize and manage the process. Due to being international university, the university has to have the VA that able to meet international standards. Chosen international university has an exchange program where students go to the partner universities not to study abroad but exchange the culture. This exchange program usually involves academic staff of the university and the students, but not the administrative ones.

It is planned to hold such exchange program with the manager of Student Services Unit in summer. The designed training program for the manager will be going to partner University with students, whose academic performance is high and are active in social life of the university. She will be given a task to learn more about the structure of the Volunteers Associations in partner university. It is required to develop the procedure and documentation for Volunteers Association to open it at the chosen university officially. Moreover, to study the structure of Student Services system and the ways of engaging students is the next aim put in front of a manger.

The reason for choosing partner university is that the rules and regulations inside of both institute are the same and the organizational structure was adapted for the branch. The exchange program is planned to last one week and the following is the plan on how to spend the time effectively:

- Day 1 – Traveling from Tashkent to partner university, sightseeing tour
- Day 2 – Welcome reception, Campus tour, Orientation of the activities
- Day 3 – Class meeting: Presentation on cultural aspects of both countries
- Day 4 – Class meeting: Lecture on “Benefits of Volunteers Association and the reasons for joining”
- Day 5 – Group work activities, cultural exchange between students
- Day 6 – Field trip, farewell party
- Day 7 – Traveling from abroad to Tashkent

After coming back to the Tashkent, participants of the program will be given some time to make a report about the conducted learning and development activities.

5.2 Training for the assistant manager of Student Services Unit

The above training session has been designed and developed for learner to gain some skills and competences to stay is her position. However, Assistant manager of SSU stressed that she has all the necessary skills, knowledge and abilities to perform her task efficiently and her performance appraisals confirms the view. For this reason, she wants to be promoted within a year. Nonetheless, in order to be promoted she is lacking strong management and leadership skills. The below training session is dedicated to improve management and leadership competences.

In order to teach leadership and management skills, online course named “Leadership and Management Skills Training” session will be offered to assistant manager of SSU to participate. The James Bruce, who is the SEO Expert, Marketer, Author and Teacher, has developed the session. According to Udemy (2024), Jim's diverse courses show his enthusiasm and expertise in a wide range of subjects. He has been making an online career for a decade and his passions range from on-page SEO, authoring books and movie screenplays, to Word Press tutorials. Moreover, he is regarded as a

specialist in the Udemy organic search, routinely ranking courses in every genre on Page 1. The session was accessed by 3414 users from 2019 to 2024 (Udemy, 2024). The title of the course is ‘First Steps to Leadership: 10 Qualities of Great Leaders’. Followings are the agenda of the training session (adopted from Bruce (2019)):

- What is a leader?
- Leadership Skills – Inspire your team
- Does a leader use Incentives?
- Develop a leader’s charisma - authority
- How leaders deal with a crisis?
- Is it better to be feared or liked?
- How to handle difficult people?
- Choosing people for your team
- Personality types
- Conclusion

University will take over the purchase of the course. According to Udemy (2024), after finishing the course, learner will be given a certificate of completion.

6.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study delved into the talent development needs within the Student Services Unit (SSU) of an international university in Tashkent through qualitative methods, focusing on semi-structured interviews. The insights gleaned from interviews with key personnel, including the SSU Manager and Assistant Manager, shed light on critical areas requiring attention, such as the establishment of a well-structured Volunteers Association (VA) and the enhancement of management and leadership skills. The proposed training programs tailored to the specific needs of each staff member aim to address these gaps effectively. By leveraging exchange programs and online courses, the university can equip its employees with the necessary competencies to fulfil their roles efficiently and contribute to organizational success. These initiatives not only empower individual career progression but also bolster organizational effectiveness and student satisfaction, aligning with the overarching goals of the institution.

REFERENCES

1. Francis, Helen, and Anne Keegan. “(PDF) the Changing Face of HRM: In Search of Balance.” ResearchGate, June 2006, www.researchgate.net/publication/229545568_The_changing_face_of_HRM_In_search_of_balance. [Accessed 18 Feb. 2024].
2. Ludwikovska, Kamila. “(PDF) the Effectiveness of Training Needs Analysis and Its Relation to Employee Efficiency.” *ResearchGate*, Dec. 2018, www.researchgate.net/publication/330184114_The_effectiveness_of_training_needs_analysis_and_its_relation_to_employee_efficiency. [Accessed 18 Feb. 2024].
3. Rezende Ferreira, Rodrigo , and G.S Abbad. “(PDF) Training Needs Assessment: Where We Are and Where We Should Go.” ResearchGate, Mar. 2013, www.researchgate.net/publication/262664679_Training_Needs_Assessment_Where_We_Are_and_Where_We_Should_Go. Accessed 18 Feb. 2024.

4. Udemy. (2024). Leadership Training - Leadership and Management Skills. Udemy. Available from <https://www.udemy.com/course/leadership-skills-training-how-to-become-a-great-leader> [Accessed 10 January 2024].